

SUPPORTING DATA FOR THE FOLLOWING PAPER PUBLISHED
IN THE JOURNAL OF DAIRY SCIENCE

<https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2021-20699>

**Nutrient digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows
when saturated free fatty acid supplements are included in diets: A meta-
analysis**

J. M. dos Santos Neto*, J. de Souza[†], A. L. Lock*¹

*Department of Animal Science, Michigan State University, East Lansing, MI 48824

[†]Perdue AgriBusiness, Salisbury, MD 21804

¹Corresponding author: Adam L. Lock
2265 Anthony Hall, 474 S. Shaw Lane
East Lansing, MI 48824
E-mail: allock@msu.edu

INTERPRETATIVE SUMMARY

Nutrient digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows when saturated free fatty acid supplements are included in diets: a meta-analysis. *By dos Santos Neto et al.* Our first objective was to perform a meta-analysis and meta-regression to evaluate the effects of saturated free fatty acid supplements on nutrient digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows. Our second objective was to evaluate whether experimental design impacts production responses to supplementation with saturated free fatty acids. Our results indicate no reason for the restrictive use of change-over designs in supplementation studies and meta-analysis with saturated fatty acid supplements. Lactating dairy cows responded better to fatty acid supplements enriched in C16:0 compared to those containing C16:0 and C18:0.

Supplemental Table S1. List of the studies used and their experimental designs.

Authors	Year	Design ¹	Fat type ²	Design type	
				Continuous	Change-over
Schauff and Clark	1989	LSD	MIX		X
Wu et al.	1993	CBD	MIX	X	
Wu et al.	1994	CBD	MIX	X	
Elliott et al.	1995	LSD	MIX		X
Grummer et al.	1996	LSD	MIX		X
Grum et al.	1996	LSD	MIX		X
Chan et al.	1997a	LSD	MIX		X
Chan et al.	1997b	CBD	MIX	X	
Simas et al.	1998	CBD	MIX	X	
Moallem et al.	2007a	CRD	MIX	X	
Moallem et al.	2007b	CRD	MIX	X	
Mosley et al.	2007	LSD	PALM		X
Ganj Khanlou et al.	2008	LSD	PALM		X
Warntjes et al.	2008	LSD	PALM		X
Weiss and Pinos-Rodríguez	2009	CBD	MIX	X	
Ballou et al.	2009	CRD	MIX	X	
Wang et al.	2010	CBD	MIX	X	
Weiss et al.	2011	LSD	MIX		X
Piantoni et al.	2013	COD	PALM		X
Lock et al.	2013	COD	PALM		X
Rico et al.	2014b	LSD	PALM		X
Piantoni et al.	2015b	CBD	MIX	X	
Boerman et al.	2015	COD	PALM		X
de Souza et al.	2016	LSD	PALM		X
de Souza et al.	2017	LSD	PALM		X
Rico et al.	2017	LSD	PALM		X
Ylioja et al.	2018	LSD	MIX		X
de Souza and Lock	2018	CBD	PALM	X	
de Souza and Lock	2019a	CBD	PALM	X	
de Souza and Lock	2019b	LSD	PALM		X
de Souza et al.	2019	CBD	PALM	X	
Western et al.	2020	COD	MIX		X
Western et al.	2020	COD	PALM		X

¹ CBD = completely block design; COD = crossover design; CRD = completely randomized design; LSD = Latin square design.

² MIX (C16:0+C18:0-enriched [$\geq$ 80%] supplements), and PALM (C16:0-enriched [$\geq$ 80%] supplements) in diet DM.

Supplemental Table S2. Meta 1: Descriptive statistic of variables according to experimental design in the data set

Item	Change-over ¹							Continuous ²						
	n		Overall					n		Overall				
	CON ³	SFFA ⁴	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	CON ³	SFFA ⁴	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD
DIM	26	32	129	132	26	249	61.5	18	19	53.3	132	1.00	184	56.9
DMI, kg/d	26	32	25.3	25.9	19.1	30.8	3.20	18	19	24.1	24.7	18.4	30.8	3.57
Nutrient Digestibility, %														
DM	12	13	65.0	65.6	54.8	72.1	3.35	9	11	64.1	64.0	59.6	69.8	2.53
NDF	13	18	44.9	44.8	31.2	60.2	8.15	10	12	43.5	44.6	35.1	57.1	6.04
Total FA ⁵	12	17	71.3	71.8	55.3	81.4	7.12	8	8	77.6	76.2	72.3	83.4	3.18
Milk Yield, kg/d														
Milk	26	32	37.5	35.2	22.8	47.6	7.20	18	19	40.1	44.4	26.4	58.3	8.86
Fat	25	31	1.33	1.32	0.83	1.81	0.26	17	18	1.47	1.56	0.88	2.31	0.47
Protein	26	32	1.16	1.14	0.80	1.46	0.21	17	18	1.22	1.29	0.79	1.85	0.29
3.5% FCM ⁶	25	31	38.0	36.1	25.7	49.2	6.99	17	18	41.4	44.4	25.7	62.5	11.2
ECM ⁷	25	31	38.1	36.4	26.2	48.1	6.91	17	18	41.0	44.3	25.7	61.3	10.9
Milk Content, g/100g														
Fat	26	32	3.66	3.73	2.84	4.83	0.49	17	18	3.67	3.65	2.93	4.89	0.54
Protein	26	32	3.13	3.14	2.79	3.69	0.21	17	18	3.02	2.99	2.78	3.43	0.17
BW, kg	13	16	651	633	416	751	104	12	12	665	675	558	847	72.7
BW change, kg/d	5	7	0.43	0.36	0.02	0.78	0.25	10	10	0.35	0.31	-2.65	1.17	0.87
BCS	6	9	3.25	3.25	2.93	3.58	0.18	9	9	3.12	3.11	2.71	3.53	0.22
Energy output ⁸ , Mcal/d														
Milk	25	30	26.3	25.1	18.1	33.2	4.71	17	18	28.3	29.6	17.8	42.0	7.55

Maintenance	13	16	10.2	10.1	7.37	11.5	1.28	12	12	10.5	10.6	9.20	12.6	0.85
Milk Fatty Acid Yield ⁹ , g/d														
De novo	17	22	323	23.6	169	428	3.33	13	13	339	24.2	197	488	3.81
Mixed	17	22	481	36.5	250	724	4.26	14	14	466	32.8	256	763	2.43
Preformed	17	22	420	30.8	236	596	4.62	14	14	549	38.9	351	984	4.71
Milk Fatty Acid Content ⁹ , g/100g														
De novo	17	22	24.6	311	18.1	31	90	13	13	23.5	417	15.4	31	105
Mixed	17	22	36.7	499	28.5	44.5	146	14	14	33.5	546	28	39.6	150
Preformed	17	22	32.1	405	23.8	46.4	102	14	14	38.9	579	30.9	47.9	177

¹ Studies with Latin Square design and crossover design.

² Studies with completely randomized design (CRD) and completely block design (CBD).

³ CON = control diet, no supplemental fat.

⁴ SFFA = $\geq$ 80% saturated free fatty acid supplements ($\frac{1}{2}$ (MIX + PALM)) included at $\leq$ 3% diet DM.

⁵ Total fatty acids.

⁶ 3.5 % FCM = $[(0.4324 \times \text{kg milk}) + (16.216 \times \text{kg milk fat})]$ (NRC, 2001).

⁷ ECM = $[(0.327 \times \text{kg milk}) + (12.95 \times \text{kg milk fat}) + (7.20 \times \text{kg milk protein})]$ (Tyrrell and Reid, 1965).

⁸ Milk NEL (Mcal/d) = $[9.29 \times \text{fat} (\%) + 5.63 \times \text{true protein} (\%) + 3.95 \times \text{lactose} (\%)]$; NEL maintenance (Mcal/d) = $\text{BW}^{0.75} (\text{kg}) \times 0.08$ (Mcal/kg) (NRC, 2001).

⁹ De novo FA originate from mammary de novo synthesis (<16 carbons), preformed FA originated from extraction from plasma (>16 carbons), and mixed FA originate from both sources (C16:0 plus C16:1).

Supplemental Table S3. Meta 2: Descriptive statistic of the variables according to treatment diets in the data set.

Item	CON ¹						MIX ²						PALM ³					
	n	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	n	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	n	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD
DIM	44	94.6	92.0	1.00	249	71.4	28	76.3	80	1.00	193	59.9	23	136	146	1.00	249	69.5
DMI, kg/d	44	24.8	24.5	19.2	30.6	3.24	28	24.8	23.9	18.4	30.8	3.43	23	24.9	26.4	22.1	30.8	2.55
Nutrient Digestibility,%																		
DM	21	64.1	64.3	54.8	68.6	3.25	13	64.9	65.6	61.6	69.8	2.63	11	65.7	65.6	61.1	72.1	2.88
NDF	23	43.3	41.4	31.2	59.0	7.64	13	44.3	52.0	36.1	60.2	7.28	17	47.8	44.7	33.4	55.1	5.68
Total FA ⁴	20	74.4	75.8	55.3	83.4	7.81	8	69.9	72.1	66.5	76.0	3.87	17	71.5	74.6	58.9	81.4	6.19
Milk Yield, kg/d																		
Milk	44	37.6	37.3	22.8	55.0	8.51	28	36.3	35.0	24.2	48.4	7.98	23	41.6	42.0	29.0	58.3	7.78
Fat	42	1.35	1.30	0.83	2.22	9.54	27	1.32	1.19	0.86	2.31	0.35	22	1.60	1.51	1.10	2.31	0.33
Protein	43	1.16	1.14	0.79	1.66	9.23	27	1.09	1.08	0.82	1.53	0.23	23	1.30	1.32	0.93	1.85	0.23
3.5% FCM ⁵	42	38.6	37.2	25.7	57.7	9.54	27	39.5	34.8	26.8	58.1	8.83	22	40.9	43.2	30.4	62.5	8.50
ECM ⁶	42	38.5	37.2	25.7	56.8	9.23	27	39.3	34.7	26.8	56.6	8.51	22	40.5	43.4	30.4	61.3	8.26
ECM/DMI, kg/kg	42	1.55	1.44	1.05	2.66	0.35	27	1.57	1.45	1.15	2.46	0.32	22	1.62	1.53	1.32	2.58	0.27
Milk Content, g/100g																		
Fat	43	3.62	3.59	2.84	4.83	0.50	27	3.69	3.6	2.84	4.89	0.59	23	3.87	3.92	3.22	4.89	0.38
Protein	43	3.12	3.09	2.78	3.69	0.23	27	3.07	3.0	2.79	3.58	0.24	23	3.15	3.14	2.92	3.41	0.14
BW, kg	25	657	10.2	416	847	1.20	16	657	9.9	416	792	1.24	12	656	10.8	669	751	0.29
BW change, kg/d	15	0.38	0.32	-1.89	0.82	0.63	8	0.37	0.41	-	1.17	0.37	9	0.39	0.33	-2.65	0.65	1.03
BCS ⁷	15	3.19	3.19	2.71	3.57	0.21	6	3.26	3.25	2.89	3.58	0.32	12	3.14	3.24	2.93	3.29	0.14
Energy output ⁷ , Mcal/d																		

Milk	42	26.6	25.9	17.8	39.9	6.38	27	27.1	23.9	18.6	39.6	5.78	21	28.1	28.6	20.8	42.0	5.91	
Maintenance	25	10.4	10.2	7.37	12.6	1.20	16	10.3	9.89	7.37	11.9	1.24	12	10.4	10.8	10.52	11.5	0.29	
Milk Fatty Acid Yield ⁸ , g/d																			
De novo	30	338	348	180	520	105	17	318	263	184	506	122	18	315	369	203	499	77.9	
Mixed	31	436	473	267	656	119	18	453	402	284	624	125	18	569	633	428	814	110	
Preformed	31	479	467	252	963	175	18	521	472	293	736	141	18	476	445	331	1049	194	
Milk Fatty Acid Content ⁸ , g/100g																			
De novo	30	25.7	25.3	16.6	31.0	3.38	17	24.0	24.2	18.1	28.4	3.60	18	22.5	22.5	15.4	26.2	2.58	
Mixed	31	33.6	32.2	28.0	38.1	2.57	18	34.2	33.5	30.3	37.3	2.28	18	39.8	40.9	33.2	44.5	3.27	
Preformed	31	34.5	32.9	25.4	47.9	5.96	18	36.1	35.7	32.0	44.2	4.09	18	32.5	29.9	23.8	45.8	6.25	

¹ CON = control diets, no supplemental fat,

² MIX = diets with C16:0+C18:0-enriched ($\geq 80\%$) supplements included at $\leq 3\%$ diet DM

³ PALM = diets with C16:0-enriched ($\geq 80\%$) supplements included at $\leq 3\%$ diet DM.

⁴ Total fatty acids.

⁵ 3.5 % FCM = $[(0.4324 \times \text{kg milk}) + (16.216 \times \text{kg milk fat})]$ (NRC, 2001).

⁶ ECM = $[(0.327 \times \text{kg milk}) + (12.95 \times \text{kg milk fat}) + (7.20 \times \text{kg milk protein})]$ (Tyrrell and Reid, 1965).

⁷ Milk NEL (Mcal/d) = $[9.29 \times \text{fat} (\%) + 5.63 \times \text{true protein} (\%) + 3.95 \times \text{lactose} (\%)]$; NEL maintenance (Mcal/d) = $\text{BW}0.75 (\text{kg}) \times 0.08 (\text{Mcal/kg})$ (NRC, 2001). De novo FA originate from mammary de novo synthesis (<16 carbons), preformed FA originated from extraction from plasma (>16 carbons), and mixed FA originate from both sources (C16:0 plus C16:1).

⁸ De novo FA originate from mammary de novo synthesis (<16 carbons), preformed FA originated from extraction from plasma (>16 carbons), and mixed FA originate from both sources (C16:0 plus C16:1).

Supplemental Table S4. Meta 2: Descriptive statistic of individual milk fatty acids according to treatment diets in the data set

Item	CON ¹						MIX ²						PALM					
	n	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	n	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	n	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD
Milk Fatty Acid Yield, g/d																		
C4:0	28	41.0	44.9	13.8	74.0	17.4	15	43.4	38.2	14.3	77.1	22.8	18	44.5	46.4	31.5	82.0	13.8
C6:0	30	28.6	29.5	16.3	49.2	9.69	17	28.8	26.4	18.7	51.1	12.6	18	28.2	29.8	19.1	47.6	7.32
C8:0	30	18.0	18.6	8.63	33.8	5.85	17	17.1	17.1	10.1	26.3	5.96	18	16.3	17.8	10.1	28.1	4.88
C10:0	30	42.6	44.8	26.1	65.4	12.7	17	38.3	38.6	21.3	58.6	13.7	18	37.1	41.6	21.6	62.6	11.2
C12:0	30	50.9	51.2	32.1	75.8	14.9	17	44	46.0	26.2	65.3	14.7	18	43.7	47.7	24.6	67.8	13.2
C14:0	30	152	156	95.6	230	43.6	17	143	124	90.2	215	48.4	18	141	164	87.9	218	36.4
C14:1	16	12.3	13.9	9.96	20.8	4.82	9	11.9	14.8	10.7	18.7	3.74	13	11.6	10.2	8.65	16.0	2.54
C16:0	31	411	451	247	623	110	17	444	402	264	587	115	18	532	608	398	774	105
C16:1	27	23.1	24.0	14.1	50.7	9.30	14	23.5	29.0	17.1	41.9	8.77	18	26.2	26.5	19.0	52.0	8.11
C18:0	31	127	129	58.6	263	51.7	17	152	131	86.1	211	36.9	17	121	132	69.5	256	56.8
C18:1	31	275	293	150	640	114	18	296	299	175	466	93.5	18	291	292	219	693	122
C18:2	29	42.0	47.9	19.8	68.6	15.8	18	40.0	48.5	21.2	66.5	15.7	14	39.4	40.1	26.9	63.1	12.6
C18:3	23	6.14	7.93	2.64	11.0	2.79	13	5.88	9.43	2.70	10.9	3.01	13	5.71	4.72	2.93	8.78	2.14
Milk Fatty Acid Content, g/100g																		
C4:0	28	3.07	3.10	1.20	4.13	0.72	15	3.18	3.73	1.57	4.33	1.04	18	3.10	2.98	2.51	3.58	0.25
C6:0	30	2.17	2.20	1.76	2.91	0.30	17	2.14	2.40	1.74	2.87	0.34	18	2.02	1.94	1.62	2.09	0.14
C8:0	29	1.37	1.31	1.04	2.40	0.31	17	1.27	1.24	0.95	1.90	0.27	17	1.20	1.11	0.91	1.80	0.21
C10:0	30	3.22	3.15	1.63	4.60	0.56	17	2.76	2.84	1.92	4.20	0.62	18	2.68	2.67	1.46	3.23	0.44
C12:0	30	3.84	3.69	1.69	5.70	0.78	17	3.14	3.06	2.36	5.00	0.73	18	3.18	3.04	1.55	3.87	0.61
C14:0	30	11.7	11.6	7.01	14.6	1.61	17	10.5	10.0	8.75	13.5	1.53	18	10.2	10.2	6.47	12.0	1.44
C14:1	17	0.94	0.91	0.70	1.63	0.31	10	0.85	1.02	0.60	1.40	0.26	13	0.84	0.79	0.54	0.92	0.11

C16:0	31	31.7	30.6	25.9	36.2	2.66	18	32.9	32.3	28.2	35.4	2.49	18	37.8	38.7	31.6	43.1	3.35
C16:1	27	1.71	1.90	1.15	2.52	0.42	14	1.70	2.05	1.68	2.45	0.21	18	1.86	1.66	1.35	2.86	0.35
C18:0	31	9.74	9.33	6.76	13.8	1.87	18	10.9	10.4	8.88	14.1	1.33	18	8.74	8.70	6.83	12.8	1.70
C18:1	31	21.6	21.2	16.9	31.9	3.65	18	22.2	22.4	19.4	26.6	2.13	18	20.7	19.4	16.6	30.3	3.80
C18:2	29	3.33	2.94	2.06	5.70	1.01	18	3.13	2.83	2.26	5.21	1.04	14	3.05	2.41	2.02	4.20	0.58
C18:3	23	0.46	0.47	0.27	1.02	0.22	12	0.43	0.56	0.25	0.95	0.25	13	0.41	0.33	0.22	0.51	0.09

¹ CON = control diets, no supplemental fat,

² MIX = diets with C16:0+C18:0-enriched ($\geq 80\%$) supplements included at $\leq 3\%$ diet DM

³ PALM = diets with C16:0-enriched ($\geq 80\%$) supplements included at $\leq 3\%$ diet DM.

Supplemental Table S5. Meta 2: Individual milk fatty acid yields and contents of lactating dairy cows fed treatment diets.

Item	Treatments ¹			SEM	n ²	Variance ³		P-value ⁴
	Control	MIX	PALM			$\hat{\sigma}_s$	$\hat{\sigma}_e$	
Milk Fatty Acid Yield, g/d								
C4:0	41.0 ^b	43.4 ^{ab}	44.5 ^a	3.61	16(61)	0.45	0.11	0.04
C6:0	28.6	28.8	28.2	1.85	17(65)	7.55	2.29	0.82
C8:0	18.0 ^a	17.1 ^{ab}	16.3 ^b	1.23	17(65)	4.97	1.71	<0.01
C10:0	42.6 ^a	38.3 ^b	37.1 ^b	2.60	17(65)	0.29	0.18	<0.01
C12:0	50.9 ^a	44.0 ^b	43.7 ^b	3.14	17(65)	0.34	0.22	<0.01
C14:0	152 ^a	143 ^{ab}	141 ^b	9.33	17(65)	1.14	0.49	0.02
C14:1	12.3	11.9	11.6	0.83	11(41)	2.02	1.83	0.54
C16:0	411 ^c	444 ^b	532 ^a	25.0	17(67)	3.28	0.96	<0.01
C16:1	23.1 ^b	23.5 ^b	26.2 ^a	1.84	15(59)	0.22	0.09	<0.01
C18:0	127 ^b	152 ^a	121 ^b	10.3	17(67)	1.35	0.4	<0.01
C18:1	275 ^b	296 ^a	291 ^{ab}	20.8	17(67)	2.69	0.94	0.05
C18:2	42.0 ^a	40.0 ^{ab}	39.4 ^b	3.14	16(61)	0.38	0.14	0.09
C18:3	6.14 ^a	5.88 ^{ab}	5.71 ^b	0.69	14(51)	2.56	0.48	0.04
Milk Fatty Acid Content, g/100g								
C4:0	3.07	3.18	3.10	0.14	16(61)	0.51	0.14	0.40
C6:0	2.17 ^a	2.14 ^a	2.02 ^b	0.06	17(65)	0.22	0.09	<0.01
C8:0	1.37 ^a	1.27 ^b	1.20 ^c	0.07	17(65)	0.28	0.06	<0.01
C10:0	3.22 ^a	2.76 ^b	2.68 ^b	0.15	17(65)	0.48	0.30	<0.01
C12:0	3.84 ^a	3.14 ^b	3.18 ^b	0.19	17(65)	0.65	0.39	<0.01
C14:0	11.7 ^a	10.5 ^b	10.2 ^b	0.39	17(65)	1.43	0.61	<0.01
C14:1	0.94 ^a	0.85 ^{ab}	0.84 ^b	0.08	11(41)	0.2	0.12	0.10
C16:0	31.7 ^b	32.9 ^b	37.8 ^a	0.79	17(67)	2.63	1.01	<0.01
C16:1	1.71 ^b	1.70 ^b	1.86 ^a	0.11	15(59)	0.36	0.15	0.01
C18:0	9.74 ^b	10.9 ^a	8.74 ^c	0.39	17(67)	1.40	0.63	<0.01
C18:1	21.6	22.2	20.7	0.86	17(67)	2.81	1.90	0.17
C18:2	3.33 ^a	3.13 ^{ab}	3.05 ^b	0.25	16(61)	0.95	0.22	<0.01
C18:3	0.46 ^a	0.43 ^b	0.41 ^b	0.06	14(51)	0.2	0.02	<0.01

^{a-c} For the effect of treatment, means in a row with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$). Separation conducted only if treatment effect was $P < 0.10$.

¹CON = control diets, no supplemental fat, MIX = diets with C16:0+C18:0-enriched ($\geq 80\%$) supplements included at $\leq 3\%$ diet DM, and PALM = diets with C16:0-enriched ($\geq 80\%$) supplements included at $\leq 3\%$ diet DM.

² Number of studies (overall number of treatment means). More information in Supplementary Table 4.

³ $\hat{\sigma}_s$ = square root of the estimated study variance; $\hat{\sigma}_e$ = square root of the estimated residual variance.

⁴ P-values refer to the effect of treatment.

Supplemental Table S6. Meta 3: Individual milk fatty acid yields and contents of lactating dairy cows for 1-percentage-unit increase of saturated free fatty acid supplements (SFFA) in diet DM.

Item	Inclusion/1%		SEM	n ²	Variance ³		P-value ⁴		
	MIX	PALM			$\hat{\sigma}_s$	$\hat{\sigma}_e$	MIX/ 1%DM	PALM/ 1%DM	MIX vs.
Milk Fatty Acid Yield, g/d									
C4:0	0.47	2.46	0.61	15(30)	1.56	1.06	0.51	<0.01	0.01
C6:0	0.11	-0.11	0.27	16(32)	0.52	0.67	0.73	0.63	0.53
C8:0	-	-0.73	0.20	16(32)	0.48	0.39	0.01	<0.01	0.65
C10:0	-	-2.94	0.66	16(32)	1.83	1.16	0.01	<0.01	0.31
C12:0	-	-3.67	0.86	16(32)	2.21	1.65	0.01	<0.01	0.49
C14:0	-	-5.65	1.30	16(32)	2.66	3.17	<0.01	<0.01	0.89
C14:1	-	-0.20	0.32	10(22)	0.50	0.75	0.15	0.48	0.37
C16:0	14.7	71.7	6.74	17(33)	17.22	5.15	0.07	<0.01	<0.01
C16:1	0.10	2.05	0.29	14(29)	0.00	1.05	0.77	<0.01	<0.01
C18:0	10.4	-2.50	1.62	17(33)	2.62	3.50	<0.01	0.05	<0.01
C18:1	10.3	4.15	1.18	17(33)	2.08	3.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
C18:2	-	-0.57	0.45	15(29)	1.39	0.58	0.42	0.21	0.64
C18:3	-	-0.05	0.11	13(26)	0.29	0.15	0.55	0.65	0.81
Milk Fatty Acid Content, g/100g									
C4:0	0.03	0.02	0.03	15(30)	0.05	0.05	0.36	0.34	0.72
C6:0	-	-0.09	0.01	16(32)	0.00	0.04	0.45	<0.01	<0.01
C8:0	-	-0.10	0.01	16(32)	0.01	0.04	0.01	<0.01	0.01
C10:0	-	-0.33	0.05	16(32)	0.13	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	0.03
C12:0	-	-0.30	0.04	16(32)	0.08	0.10	<0.01	<0.01	0.53
C14:0	-	-0.86	0.07	16(32)	0.16	0.14	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
C14:1	-	-0.04	0.02	10(22)	0.03	0.03	0.16	0.02	0.73
C16:0	0.64	3.41	0.24	17(33)	0.60	0.20	0.03	<0.01	<0.01
C16:1	-	0.09	0.02	14(29)	0.02	0.06	0.73	<0.01	0.01
C18:0	0.60	-0.55	0.07	17(33)	0.03	0.26	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
C18:1	0.57	-0.37	0.17	17(33)	0.32	0.45	0.01	0.02	<0.01
C18:2	-	-0.16	0.03	15(29)	0.08	0.05	0.05	<0.01	0.05
C18:3	-	-0.03	0.00	13(26)	0.00	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.36

¹ Effect of 1-percentage-unit increase of MIX (C16:0+C18:0-enriched [$\geq 80\%$] supplements), and PALM (C16:0-enriched [$\geq 80\%$] supplements) in diet DM.

² Number of studies (the resulting number of observations obtained from the difference between MIX or PALM diet means minus control diet [CON] means used in the meta-regression). More information in Supplementary Table 4.

³ $\hat{\sigma}_s$ = square root of the estimated study variance; $\hat{\sigma}_e$ = square root of the estimated residual variance.

⁴ P-values were used to test if the supplementations of MIX (MIX/1%DM) and PALM (PALM/1%DM) per 1-percentage-unit increase in diet DM were different from zero (null hypothesis: 1% of FA supplement addition has no effect), and to compare the MIX vs PALM.

* We reviewed citations from previous reviews related to saturated free fatty acids (SFFA) supplementation: Firkins and Eastridge, 1994; Allen, 2000; Loften and Cornelius, 2004; Onetti and Grummer, 2004; Rabiee et al., 2012; Loften et al. 2014; Boerman et al., 2015a; Dórea and Armentano, 2017; Hu et al., 2017; and Weld and Armentano, 2017.

** Papers were searched for in electronic databases (Scirus, CAB, Cambridge University Press, Elsevier, Google Scholar, PubMed, Science Direct, and Springer) and in the search engines of Animal Feed Science and Technology, Animal Production Science, Animal, Brazilian Journal of Animal Science, Journal of Animal Physiology and Animal Nutrition, Journal of Animal Science, Journal of Dairy Research, Journal of Dairy Science, Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture, Livestock Science, and The Professional Animal Scientist.

*** We divided SFFA into C16:0-enriched supplements (PALM, FA supplement with $\geq 80\%$ C16:0) and C16:0+C18:0-enriched supplements (MIX, FA supplement with $\geq 80\%$ C16:0 + C18:0). Main reasons for exclusion were: 1) SFFA inclusion $> 3\%$ diet DM, 2) absence of non-fat supplemented control diets, 3) inclusion of other fat supplements in addition to PALM or MIX, and 4) studies using fat supplements rather than PALM or MIX.

Supplemental Figure S1. The PRISMA flow diagram from the initial search and screening to the final selection of studies included for the meta-analysis and meta-regression on the effects of CSPF on nutrient digestibility and production responses of lactating dairy cows (Page et al., 2021; <http://www.prisma-statement.org/PRISMAStatement/FlowDiagram>).

Supplemental Figure S2. A. Standard Funnel plots for some of the key responses analyzed (Sterne and Harbord, 2004; Rabiee et al., 2012). **B.** Contour-Enhanced Funnel Plot for some of the key responses analyzed. The white region (unshaded) region in the middle corresponds to P -values greater than 0.10, the dark gray-shaded region corresponds to P -values between 0.10 and 0.05, the medium gray-shaded region corresponds to P -values between 0.05 and 0.01, and the region outside of the funnel corresponds to P -values below 0.01 (Sterne and Egger, 2001; Peters et al., 2008; https://www.metafor-project.org/doku.php/plots:contour_enhanced_funnel_plot).